

Appendix H – Third Version of the MPO

MODEL FOR PROJECTS OBSERVATORIES (MPO)

Third Version

1. INTRODUCTION

There is no consensus definition in the literature for the concept of “observatories”, however, Vieira et al. (2020), when analyzing a considerable amount of work published in the literature, suggested the following definition: an instrument, mechanism, process or organizational unit that makes it possible to observe something, providing transparency through collection, consolidation, storage, study, research, analysis, sharing, monitoring and dissemination of data, information and knowledge from (and to) a given community. In an internet search it is possible to identify observatories related to the most varied areas of knowledge, for example, education, security, social, public health, among others. Table 1 presents examples of observatories with pages available on the web.

Table 1 – Examples of Observatories

Observatory	Web page
Observatory of the National Education Plan	https://observatoriodopne.org.br/
National Road Safety Observatory	https://www.onsv.org.br/
Brazilian Social Observatory	https://osbrasil.org.br/
Covid-19 Observatory	https://www.ufpe.br/observatorio-covid-19
Web Observatory	https://www.webscience.org/web-observatory/
urban Observatory	https://www.urbanobservatory.org/

Source: Prepared by the author (2021).

Trzeciak (2009) states that observatories can develop their own models for their operations, according to the purpose they intend to serve. Therefore, this document aims to present a proposal for a conceptual model for observatories developed in the context of projects, the Model for Projects Observatories (MPO). The MPO comprises project observatories from the perspective of information systems, that is, a set of interrelated components that collect, process, store and distribute information intended to support decision-making, coordination and control (LAUDON and LAUDON, 2014). Furthermore, the MPO is developed from a sociotechnical approach, conceptualizing project observatories from a set of users and technologies in a social context (BROWN, 2017).

The MPO is a conceptual model for project observatories, Johnson and Henderson (2002) state that a conceptual model is a high-level description of how a “system is organized and operates”. Thus, for Sokolowski and Banks (2010), a conceptual model is often used to demonstrate the general functionality of a system, interpreting the real world of the system with its specifications and with a representation, which can be carried out from a textual description. However, preferably in graphic form.

The first version of the MPO was developed through two studies: (1) execution of a set of exploratory studies, which aimed to execute pilot projects of project observatories; and (2) systematic mapping of the literature on observatories. The second version of the MPO is the result of the evolution of the first version of the model based on suggestions

for improvements collected from the execution of three focus groups with experts in projects and observatories. The third and final version of the MPO, presented in this document, is the result of the evaluation and consequent evolution of the second version of the model carried out through a *survey* with participants in the project observatory pilot projects (developed for the construction of the first version of the model) and with the authors identified in the systematic mapping of the literature on observatories. Appendix A presents a list of all the changes made in the first and second versions, which gave rise to the third version of the MPO.

2. MODEL ORGANIZATION

Based on studies by Moreira (2010) and Soares (2018), the MPO was structured based on a progressive conceptual differentiation technique so that the most specific concepts are placed at the bottom of the map. Then, it proceeds from bottom to top, passing through intermediate concepts, until reaching the top of the map, with more general concepts. Lines are also used to indicate relationships between concepts, vertically or horizontally. In this approach, as shown in Figure 1, there is a vertical hierarchy from top to bottom, with subordination relationships between concepts.

Figure 1 – Model structure

Source: Adapted from Moreira (2010) and Soares (2018)

MPO is made up of 3 general concepts: structures, processes and agents. These general concepts bring together a set of 8 intermediate concepts, which in turn bring together a set of 53 specific concepts. Due to the considerable number of specific concepts covered in the MPO, based on the *survey* which gave rise to the third version of the model, these concepts were grouped into two levels. These levels are related to the relevance of specific concepts for the model in question. The most relevant concepts are grouped at level 1 and the least relevant concepts are grouped at level 2.

Figure 2 illustrates the hierarchical (vertical) relationships between MPO concepts. More details about the concepts that make up the MPO are presented in the next sections.

Figure 2 – Model for Projects Observatories (MPO)

Source: Prepared by the author (2021)

The relationships between concepts can also be developed horizontally. Figure 3 shows this type of relationship between general concepts. It is through these relationships that associations, links and dependencies occur between general concepts, enabling the emergence of intermediate and specific concepts. Thus, the relationship between the Agents and the Processes (arrow 1 in Figure 3) is of the “participation” type, that is, the Agents participate in the Processes, either acting as executors or receiving the result of the processing. The relationship between Agents and Structures (arrow 2 in Figure 3) is of the “use” type, that is, the Agents use the Structures to perform a certain action in the

observatory. Finally, the relationship between Structures and Processes is of the “viability” type, that is, the Structures enable the execution of Processes in the context of observatories.

Figure 3 – Horizontal relationships between the general MPO concepts

Source: Prepared by the author (2021)

The MPO represents an ideal or conceptual vision and not a normative definition. In this sense, it is not expected/required that a project observatory expresses all aspects of the model. In fact, it can be expected that these aspects will develop/adapt over time. There is also no concern on the part of the MPO to present a sequence for its implementation, thus, the process of developing observatory projects based on the MPO is flexible and adaptable to the context of the observatory.

In an attempt to help understand the model, we developed a fictional scenario of a project observatory that sought to instantiate the concepts presented in the MPO. This scenario presents the hypothetical Observatory of Information Technology Projects of the State of Pernambuco (OPTI-PE), which proposes to be a mechanism for transparency and sharing of knowledge about public Information Technology (IT) projects, through the collection, processing and dissemination of information about IT projects, in progress or completed, developed within the scope of the Government of the State of Pernambuco. Therefore, each concept presented in this document is illustrated with a practical example, with OPTI-PE as a background.

3. STRUCTURES

This concept presents a structural and static vision of a project observatory. The following intermediate concepts are grouped into structures: components, contents, characteristics and information technology infrastructure of project observatories.

3.1. Components

The components are the structural elements that make up a project observatory. They support the execution of the observatory's processes and are made possible by the information technology infrastructure and a set of actors involved with the observatory. These components can be subdivided into:

- **Collection** : deal with the components that capture data related to projects from within organizations or their external environment.

Scenario:
OPTI-PE has a software component that integrates with project management tools used within the state government and collects data on projects automatically in these tools.

- **Dissemination** : correspond to the components responsible for disseminating and sharing the results obtained from data collection and processing.

Scenario:

As output components, OPTI-PE has a web page responsible for publishing the analyzes and reflections built in the processing component. In addition, there is a team of collaborators responsible for also publishing this information on the observatory's official profiles on social media.

- **Processing** : correspond to the components responsible for processing and converting raw data related to projects into a more meaningful form. As with the storage components, the processing components of a project observatory can be supported by a local or cloud computing infrastructure.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE uses a *Business Intelligence* (BI) system running in the cloud already consolidated in the market as a component dedicated to the treatment and processing of raw data, to generate analyzes that will be shared with the observatory's users. This tool uses the data contained in the storage component as *input* . Furthermore, there is a team of collaborators responsible for building reflections based on the *output* obtained with the BI system.

- **Storage** : they are related to the existence of a repository to store data related to the projects collected by the observatories. Project observatories may encounter two types of storage components: storage systems on the observatory's own premises or an external solution hosted by cloud computing providers.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, a component was structured to store the raw data or processing results. This component is made up of a set of servers (hardware) hosted in the cloud and a set of software (especially database systems).

- **Relationship** : deal with the components that coordinate relationships between users and their interaction with projects and the observatory. Furthermore, this concept contemplates the relationships between the project observatory and other systems.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE has a component dedicated to coordinating relationships and interactions with users and other systems. For relationships with users, OPTI-PE provides a channel, on its web page, for users to interact with the data, analyzes and reflections published about the projects. Users can make comments, publish photos, and contribute suggestions for improvements to projects. There is a team of collaborators responsible for mediating discussions, receiving suggestions for improvements and forwarding them to the sector or organization responsible for the project. Regarding the relationship with other systems, OPTI has an integration component with government project management tools and has an API where raw data can be consumed by other tools.

3.2. Content

The contents are related to the subjects covered by the project observatory. From this concept, it is possible to identify the data, information and knowledge that a project observatory collects, stores, processes and/or shares. These contents were grouped into: projects, themes, interactions and user.

- **Projects** : an observatory may contain data, information and knowledge related to projects. The studies by Porto (2021) and Santana (2021) mapped a set of attributes related to projects that can be stored by an observatory, Table 1 summarizes these attributes. This table is not intended to exhaust the identification of attributes, however, it can serve as a starting point.

Table 1. Attributes related to projects

Type	Attributes
General content	Project name, description, place of execution, type, size, objectives, description of products and services generated, bidding (for public projects), contracts, closure term (if the project has already been completed), project justifications, impacts of the project in the short and long term, project indicators, artifacts produced in the project and images/photos of the project.
Content related to project stakeholders	Name of stakeholders, role in the project, target audience of the project, details of the project team, training carried out by project teams.
Content related to project scope	Project tasks, requirements, planned scope and executed scope.
Content related to project time management	Project start date, planned and executed project end date, deliverables to be carried out and schedule status.
Content related to project costs	Estimated cost, realized cost and justification for expenses.
Content related to project risks	Identified risks, qualitative and quantitative risk analysis, risk response planning and risk monitoring.
Content related to project changes	Cost of implementing the change, cost-benefit analysis, impacts of the change on the project scope and schedule.
Content related to lessons learned from projects	Strengths and weaknesses, difficulties encountered and measures taken.

Source: Adapted from Porto (2021) and Santana (2021)

Scenario:

Based on a survey carried out with project managers and a sample of users and clients, OPTI-PE identified a set of attributes related to projects that are collected, stored, processed and disclosed. Project data included in OPTI-PE is strongly related to project management, not including, for example, the source code of developed software projects.

- **Project Themes** : a project observatory may have content related to the project theme, such as news, events and scientific research carried out on the topic.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE publishes a weekly newsletter on its website with the main news about information technology for public management published by the media. In addition, there is an area on its website dedicated to publicizing national and international events related to the topic.

- **Users** : data related to users and their interactions with project observatory content can also be understood as observatory content. This data may include, but is not limited to: basic information (for example, name, age, gender and location) projects or topics of greatest interest, role played in a project and users' comments and reactions to the content made available by the observatory.

Scenario:

At OPTI-PE, each project has a web page that brings together all information related to the project. On this page, users can interact with the project through comments. Furthermore, there is the possibility for a user to interact with other users by responding to comments. Project managers have access to these comments and, if they wish, can also interact with other users. Furthermore, a user can register with OPTI-PE to have access to a personalized area. This area makes use of recommendation algorithms to suggest projects that may be of interest to the user.

- **Observatory** : general information about the observatory should also be considered content of a project observatory. This information may include, but is not limited to, a description of the observatory and its objectives, observatory development and management team, observatory content, and project metadata.

Scenario:

There is a “About the observatory” page on OPTI-PE, where information about the observatory can be found, including a brief description and objectives, the observatory's management and development team and access to download metadata of the observatory's projects.

3.3. Characteristics

The characteristics are related to a set of properties of a project observatory. These characteristics contribute to a better understanding of its processes, components and content. It is possible to identify in a project observatory characteristics related to: access, partial data, scope, data format, interactivity, network, interoperability and sustainability.

- **Sustainability:** a project observatory needs to be planned to continue operating in the long term, otherwise the content of the observatory will only reflect a static photograph of a given moment in the projects. In this sense, a project observatory must be sustainable in the long term.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE is maintained by the Government of the State of Pernambuco and was planned and developed so that its basic functions, related to the collection, analysis and dissemination of data, information and knowledge about projects, are carried out in an automated manner with minimal human interference. , which reduces costs with employees at the observatory, making it more sustainable in the long term.

- **Scope :** a project observatory needs to have its scope clearly defined. In this sense, this scope may be related to: theme, geographic region or organization (or set of organizations) executing the projects contained in the observatories.

Scenario:

The scope of OPTI-PE is limited to information technology projects developed within the scope of the Pernambuco State Government.

- **Interoperability :** a project observatory may include mechanisms that make it capable of communicating transparently (or as close as possible) with other systems, in particular, with the systems of the observatory's target organization(s) that store data about projects.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE consumes data in a transparent and automated way from project management tools used within the State Government. Furthermore, some data is also collected automatically from open databases made available by the government. Still in this context, OPTI-PE provides an API (*Application Programming Interface*) for users interested in consuming the data and analyzes available at the observatory.

- **Access :** a project observatory can be characterized as open or semi-open. In an open observatory, all information contained therein is open to the general public, whereas in a semi-open observatory there is information that is restricted to a certain set of users.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE content is freely accessible to any audience, with no access restrictions. Thus, it can be considered an open-type project observatory.

- **Collaboration Network** : a project observatory can be characterized as a collaboration network, involving a set of actors, supported by a technological infrastructure, with a common objective: sharing data, information, and knowledge about projects.

Scenario:

It is possible to identify a set of OPTI-PE actors who form this collaboration network, among which the following stand out: IT project teams (especially project managers) from the State Government, who provide the data to be analyzed and disseminated by the observatory and receive feedback from the population; the observatory management team that works as a link between projects and the population; the users of the observatories, comprised of the population interested in IT projects developed within the scope of the Government of Pernambuco, who use the observatory as a means of obtaining more details about the projects carried out (or in progress) and as a means of collaborating with these projects, in especially, by providing feedback to the project team and government management; and, finally, the management team of the State Government of Pernambuco, which uses the observatory to support strategic decision-making based on monitoring projects and feedback from the population.

- **Security** : measures must be implemented to guarantee the security of the observatory and the data contained therein (including aspects related to data protection legislation in the country in which the observatory operates ¹).

Scenario:

OPTI-PE was designed from the beginning incorporating relevant issues related to security, among which we can highlight: access control and user authentication, definitions of permissions by observatory administrators, use of encryption in the transfer of sensitive data and definition of a policy security compliant with the LGPD (General Data Protection Law).

- **Interactivity** : a project observatory can allow interaction between users and the projects contained in the observatory. This interaction may take place (but is not limited) by registering project data, making comments on projects, participating in discussion forums, constructing analyzes or even viewing information contained in observatories.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, this interactivity feature was implemented on the pages of each project, where users can leave comments about the project, including attaching photos and videos. Furthermore, the graphs that present the analyzes of the projects contained in the observatories were built using a mechanism that allows the user to insert new parameters and customize the analysis.

- **Data Format** : data stored in a project observatory can be structured, that is, stored in an organized way (for example, project attributes), and unstructured, where the data does not have a defined structure (for example, photos and videos).

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, most project-related data is stored in a structured way. However, the data collected from users' interaction with projects is mostly unstructured data, such as photos, videos and text comments. Text mining work is done on the comments made by users to identify their feelings regarding the projects.

¹ For the Brazilian case, consider Law No. 13,709, of August 14, 2018 (General Data Protection Law – LGPD)

- **Partial Data** : the existence of incomplete or confidential information on projects requires that the project observatory be prepared to store partial data on these projects.

Scenario:

There are strategic projects at OPTI-PE, in particular, related to public security. Therefore, only partial data on these projects will be available at the observatory. Furthermore, there are some projects that have been completed for some time and the sector responsible for the project does not have much data about them. Data on this type of project will also be partially available in OPTI-PE.

3.4. Information Technology (IT) Infrastructure

IT infrastructure consists of the technological components and services that provide the basis for supporting a project observatory. This infrastructure can be understood based on the concepts: hardware, software, networks and services.

- **Data management:** corresponds to the software tools necessary for the observatory to organize, manage and process data related to projects.

Scenario:

As a storage technology, OPTI-PE chose a non-relational database hosted in the cloud. Regarding data processing and analysis construction, the software developed for OPTI-PE integrates with a well-known BI tool on the market.

- **Software:** corresponds to applications that enable the execution of processes carried out by project observatories. Laudon and Laudon (2014) divide these applications into two types: system software and application software. System software includes operating systems, while application software includes software packages and productivity tools, applications and programming languages.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE has software developed on demand to execute the observatory's processes. This software incorporates functions related to the collection, storage, treatment, processing and dissemination of data, information and knowledge about the projects. This software interfaces with a *BI system* , and automatically collects data from project management tools and open government databases. Additionally, the team uses productivity tools to organize their daily routines.

- **Networks:** corresponds to the components (including hardware and software) that enable communication, management and network operations between a project observatory and the organizations' internal and external systems.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE's current IT infrastructure is strongly service-oriented. Thus, all network resources, including hardware and software, are contracted to third parties.

- **Services:** corresponds to services performed by third parties to structure, operate and maintain the IT infrastructure of a project observatory. These services may include consultancies, internet operators, cloud computing, among others.

Scenario:

A considerable part of OPTI-PE's IT infrastructure was contracted as a service. Among them, we can highlight: outsourced service for the development of on-demand software for the

observatory; cloud infrastructure service necessary for the development and operation of this software; observatory network infrastructure.

- **Hardware:** corresponds to the physical information technology equipment used in the processes carried out by project observatories. These can include personal computers, servers, data centers, routers, switches and other devices.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE has a room with just 6 personal computers connected to the internet, one for each observatory employee, in the Strategic Projects Office, the rest of the IT infrastructure necessary for maintaining the observatory is provided via service provision.

4. PROCESS

This concept presents a project observatory from a dynamic perspective, that is, it includes concepts related to the processes that can be carried out in (and by) project observatories. The processes are executed based on the components established in the Structures concept and the actors defined in the Agents concept. Thus, these processes were grouped into: managing data and information; and produce knowledge and intelligence ².

4.1. Manage Data and Information

Data and information management groups together a set of processes related to the collection, storage, processing and availability of data and information by a project observatory.

- **To make available :** corresponds to the processes that enable users of a project observatory access the data and information collected before it undergoes any processing.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, as data is collected, it is made available, via API, in case users want to access the data on which we build our analyses.

- **Treat :** corresponds to processes related to organizing and ensuring the quality and security of data and information collected by project observatories.

Scenario:

A team of OPTI-PE collaborators is responsible for monitoring the processing of data and information collected by the observatory. This team uses a set of algorithms developed to perform this task.

- **Collect :** corresponds to processes related to identifying and collecting relevant data and information about projects and their themes. This collection can be carried out in two ways: manually, with the support of the observatory team, project stakeholders or observatory users; and automated, through the development of software components.

Scenario:

² We use verbs to name the specific concepts associated with processes, because, according to the Cambridge Dictionary (2020), a process refers to an action to be performed.

The OPTI-PE data collection process is performed by the collection component in an automated manner. Data is collected directly from project management tools and open databases made available by the government.

- **Store** : corresponds to the storage processes, in a given repository, of the data and information identified and collected by the project observatory.

Scenario:

The OPTI-PE data and information storage process is also automated by the observatory's software tool.

4.2. Produce Knowledge and Intelligence

The production of knowledge and intelligence brings together a set of processes that, based on the data and information collected about the projects, will be able to assist in the process of generating knowledge and intelligence to meet the demands of the actors involved in the project observatory.

- **Transform** : corresponds to the processes of transforming and modeling the data collected by the project observatory with the aim of discovering knowledge and intelligence to meet the demands of the observatory's users.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, the data transformation process begins immediately after data processing. A team performs these analyzes with the support of the BI tool. There is a set of routine analyses, however, new analyzes can be constructed based on demands coming from users or the observatory management team.

- **Communicate** : consists of the processes that make it possible to disseminate, share and communicate, to the actors involved with the project observatory, the entire content of the observatory, in particular, the analyzes carried out based on the data collected.

Scenario:

The OPTI-PE content communication process takes place in three different ways: all observatory content is made available to users through the observatory's web page; there is a team of collaborators responsible for publishing the observatory's content on its official social media pages; Users can share observatory content on their social networks.

- **Categorize / Classify** : concerns the processes that make it possible to identify categories and organize relationships (including hierarchical relationships) between projects.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE there is a fixed set of defined project categories, based on which projects are classified. However, new categories can be added as new projects are added. These categorization and classification processes are carried out by the observatory management team with the support of the observatory software.

- **Holding accountable** : is related to the processes that enable project observatory actors to be held accountable for their actions in the context of the observatory.

Scenario:

A term of use was defined for OPTI-PE and for the user to register with the observatory it is necessary to agree to this term. This term defines a set of rules of conduct and responsibilities to ensure the good use of the tools and content offered by the observatory. In this term of use, special attention is given to the publication of false information, in an attempt to reduce its spread. Furthermore, there is a channel where users can report situations that may violate the rules of conduct. The management team is responsible for both evaluating these reports and taking appropriate action.

- **Visualize** : consists of the processes of constructing graphic representations of data and information, through diagrams, maps and graphs in order to provide an accessible way to identify trends and patterns in the data.

Scenario:

At OPTI-PE, the observatory team maintains a set of pre-established views. However, the observatory's software tool allows the user to create their own visualizations within the established limitations.

- **Interact** : corresponds to the processes that allow the actors of a project observatory to interact with each other and with the content of the observatory.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE provides its users with the possibility of interacting with projects through comments that these users can write on project pages. On each project page, users can make (and respond to) comments about the data and analyzes constructed.

- **Monitoring** : concerns the processes that enable actors involved with a project observatory to monitor projects and their evolution over time.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE allows its users to follow the evolution of projects on the pages dedicated to each project. There the user will be able to follow a project history over time.

- **Evaluate** : consists of the processes that allow producing evaluations on projects, on the data collected and on the analyzes constructed from them. These assessments can be constructed collaboratively, by the observatory's actors, or in an automated way, based on the data collected.

Scenario:

A set of criteria were defined for OPTI-PE to evaluate projects based on the data collected. Using these criteria, a ranking with the best evaluated projects was designed and made available to observatory users.

- **Reflect** : corresponds to the processes that enable the construction of critical reflections, by the actors of the project observatory, based on the data and analyzes developed about the projects.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE offers data, information and knowledge about projects that enable its users to build critical reflections on these projects. Furthermore, OPTI-PE periodically invites project experts to reflect on the content of the observatory. These reflections are shared with users through newsletters.

- **Combine** : corresponds to the processes that make it possible to combine different data sources and patterns related to projects.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, project-related data is collected from three main sources: project management tools used by project teams; open state government databases; and information passed on by observatory users, via comments on project pages. There is a process of crossing this data to guarantee its integrity. Users have access to the result of this crossing on the projects page.

- **Collaborate** : consists of processes that allow actors involved with a project observatory to collaborate on a project, if they wish.

Scenario:

OPTI-PE has a *crowdsourcing resource* that is offered to its users in some software projects developed or financed by the State Government. For these projects, users are invited to collaborate by running tests on the software being developed. Gamification and user reward mechanisms were developed to encourage user participation.

5. AGENTS

This concept presents an observatory of projects based on its actors and the reasons that lead them to interact with the observatory. In this sense, they are grouped into agents, intermediate concepts related to actors and motivations.

5.1. Actors

Actors correspond to entities (human or systems) that, in some way, maintain a relationship (direct or indirect) with a project observatory.

- **Project Stakeholders** : according to PMI (2018), a project stakeholder can be understood as an individual, group or organization that can affect or be affected by a decision, activity or result of a project. These stakeholders may be related to, but not limited to: project team, sponsor, customers/users, suppliers and project office. In this sense, the stakeholders of a project inserted in the context of a project observatory can be considered observatory actors and can contribute to the identification of the observatory's users and target audience.

Scenario:

Stakeholders in the projects included in OPTI-PE are fundamental to the full functioning of the observatory, especially project managers. These managers are responsible for making all data and information about projects available to the observatory. The other parties interested in the projects are treated as users of the observatory.

- **Observatory Management and Development Team** : the observatory's management and development teams can also be considered actors in a project observatory. We understand the management team as the team responsible for the management, maintenance and operation of the observatory. The development team can be understood as the team responsible for designing the observatory, including the team developing and implementing the IT tools that support its operation.

Scenario:

As already mentioned, an on-demand software tool was developed for OPTI-PE, using which the observatory executes a large part of its processes. The development of this tool was outsourced to a software development company. The team responsible for developing this tool makes up the OPTI-PE development team. The observatory management team is made up of 6

employees: one observatory coordinator, two who make up the observatory software maintenance team and three who make up the observatory operations team.

- **Observatory Users** : users of a project observatory can be considered fundamental actors for the functioning of the observatory. Users can be understood as human actors who enjoy the utilities that a project observatory provides. To the extent that the stakeholders of a project make use of the resources offered by the observatory, they can also be characterized as users of the observatory.

Scenario:

In OPTI-PE, a user is understood as any person who consumes the observatory's products and services. In general, these users are made up of: students on IT courses, a community of IT professionals and researchers, the State Government management team and citizens interested in the IT products provided by the State Government. There is a user registration functionality available on the OPTI-PE page, however, even if not registered, the user has access to the observatory's content. This registration aims to better understand the user's profile, in order to recommend content that best meets that profile.

- **Systems** : non-human actors, here called systems, are represented by computational systems that are not part of the project observatory environment, however, they carry out some exchange with the observatory, either by executing some action or providing some service to the observatory.

Scenario:

At OPTI-PE, two types of computer systems interact with the observatory: project management systems used by project teams; and the State Government's open databases. These systems provide data about projects that are consumed by the observatory.

5.2. Motivations

Motivations correspond to a set of reasons that lead actors to maintain a relationship with a project observatory.

Scenario:

In an attempt to illustrate the motivations identified in the conceptual model, a set of fictitious OPTI-PE users were defined, they are:

- Antonio Gil: professor and researcher at the Federal University of Pernambuco. Develops research related to the theme “Software Projects”. Coordinates a research group currently made up of 4 researchers and 10 master's and doctoral students.
- Letícia Honório: test engineer at a company based in Porto Digital in Recife-PE. Graduated in computer science and has more than 15 years of experience participating in software development projects.
- Maria Vivian: has a degree in Business Administration and currently manages 3 software development teams at the State Government's information technology company.
- José Eliseu: graduated in Computer Science with a specialization in software engineering. He is currently the technical leader of an IT project that is being carried out by a State Government outsourced company.
- Joana Pires: has extensive experience in public management and is currently head of the government's strategic projects office.
- Cícero Pessoa: citizen from Pernambuco who currently works as a production engineer for a company in the automobile sector. Considers the participation of citizens in projects developed by the government to be fundamental.
- Felipe Tomaz: graduated in Journalism, works as a writer for the most popular newspaper in the city. He usually writes about government and technology.

- **Transparency** : they look for mechanisms that can offer transparency to projects, including the concepts underlying transparency, such as monitoring, visibility, disclosure and surveillance.

Scenario:

Joana Pires takes advantage of OPTI-PE to publicize the results achieved with projects carried out by the government to society as a whole. Cícero Pessoa, on the other hand, is always attentive to OPTI-PE as he believes that in order for citizens to be able to demand that their representatives make the best decisions, close monitoring of the projects carried out by the government is necessary.

- **Decision Making** : search for data, information and knowledge to support decision making in projects.

Scenario:

Joana Pires does not give up exploring the analyzes offered by OPTI-PE to support decisions related to projects that are under the responsibility of her office.

- **Control** : they look for mechanisms that support control over the planning and execution of projects, providing *accountability* to projects.

Scenario:

Joana Pires, as head of the strategic projects office, uses OPTI-PE to monitor and intervene together with project managers who are under her management on matters of interest to her office.

- **Interaction** : they look for mechanisms that provide interaction between project stakeholders.

Scenario:

Maria Vivian uses OPTI-PE to collect feedback from interested parties on the projects she manages.

- **Knowledge** : seek to acquire and build new knowledge based on the content made available by the project observatory.

Scenario:

Antonio Gil and his team of researchers make use of the resources offered by OPTI-PE as a source of information for the development of scientific research related to the theme "IT projects".

- **Learning** : seek to learn through collaboration and sharing of data, information and knowledge about projects.

Scenario:

Letícia Honório, whenever she can, accesses OPTI-PE content to share her knowledge about software testing and to learn from her peers who also access the observatory and share their experiences in the comments on the project pages.

- **Improvement** : search for best practices that provide improvements in projects and their management.

Scenario:

Maria Vivian is always attentive to OPTI-PE as she has already identified several good practices used in other projects and which she has introduced into the projects she manages.

- **Innovation** : seek to promote innovation in projects and in the products and services produced by them, through the knowledge acquired from a project observatory.

Scenario:

Maria Vivian uses OPTI-PE to follow news related to IT projects in order to identify innovative practices and apply them to the projects she manages.

- **Engagement** : seek more active participation of the various interested parties in the planning and execution of projects.

Scenario:

Maria Vivian believes that the more she shares project data easily and clearly, the more interested parties become engaged with her projects.

- **Dissemination** : they seek to disseminate good and bad experiences lived in projects.

Scenario:

José Eliseu participates in discussions promoted by OPTI-PE because he believes he can learn from the experiences shared by his peers.

- **Prioritization** : They look for information that helps in the project prioritization processes.

Scenario:

Joana Pires uses OPTI-PE content to help define projects that should receive more resources and, consequently, more attention from the government.

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APPENDIX A – List of changes that gave rise to the second and third versions of the MPO

This appendix presents a list of changes made between the developed versions of the model.

1. Second version:

The second version of the MPO was developed based on the adjustments made to the first version based on suggestions for improvement collected in the focus groups. There were changes in some nomenclatures used in the model, for these cases we present the previous nomenclature (used in the first version) in parentheses after the current nomenclature (used in the second version).

- **MODEL ORGANIZATION:**
 - New nomenclature used to organize the model: General Concepts (Dimension), Intermediate Concepts (Subdimension) and Specific Concepts (Elements);
 - Included more details about the model structuring process;
 - Added definitions for all concepts, including intermediate concepts;
 - Revised the entire model to avoid the use of repeated nomenclatures;
 - Included a usage scenario for all specific concepts presented in the model;

- **STRUCTURES:**
 - Added the intermediate concept “IT Infrastructure”.
 - Added the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “IT Infrastructure”: Hardware, Software, Data Management, Networks and Services.
 - Added the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Characteristics”: Network, Interoperability and Sustainability.
 - Changed the nomenclature of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Components”: Collection (Input) and Relationship (Coordination).
 - The nomenclature of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Characteristics” has been changed: Partial Data (Completeness), Scope (Delimitation) and Interactivity (Interaction).
 - Changed the nomenclature of the specific concept “User” (Observation) related to the intermediate concept “Contents”.
 - The descriptions of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Components” have been changed: Collection, Storage and Processing.

- The descriptions of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Contents” have been changed: Projects and Users.
 - Changed the description of the specific concept “Interactivity” related to the intermediate concept “Features”.
- **LAW SUIT:**
 - The nomenclature of intermediate concepts has been changed: Manage Data and Information (Data Input and Output), Produce Information and Knowledge (Data Processing).
 - Changed the nomenclature of all specific concepts to the verb format.
 - Added the specific concept “Treat” to the intermediate concept “Manage Data and Information”.
 - Removed the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Produce Information and Knowledge”: Prioritization, Prediction and Coordination.
 - The nomenclature of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Producing Knowledge and Intelligence” has been changed: Blame (Report) and Categorization/Classification (Categorize).
 - Changed the nomenclature of the specific concept “Make Available” (Share) of the intermediate concept “Manage Data and Information”.
 - The descriptions of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Manage Data and Information” have been changed: Collect, Store, Process and Make Available.
 - The descriptions of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Produce Knowledge and Intelligence” have been changed: Analyze, Visualize, Evaluate, Categorize/Classify, Debate, Reflect, Evaluate, Track, Interact, Hold Accountable and Collaborate.
 - **AGENTS:**
 - Added the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Motivations”: Accountability, Monitoring and Prioritization.
 - Added the following specific concepts related to the specific concept “Actors”: Stakeholders, Management and Development and Users.
 - Removed the specific concept “Humans” from the intermediate concept “Actors”.
 - The nomenclature of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Motivations” has been changed: Engagement (Participation) and Dissemination (Multiplication).
 - Changed the description of the specific concept “Systems” related to the intermediate concept “Actors”.
 - Changed the descriptions of the following specific concepts related to the intermediate concept “Motivations”: Knowledge, Learning, Innovation, Improvement, Decision Making, Control, Visibility, Interaction, Transparency, Dissemination and Engagement.

2. Third Version:

The third version of the MPO was developed based on the adjustments made in the second version based on *feedback* collected through the execution of a *survey* . There

were changes in some nomenclatures used in the model, for these cases we present the previous nomenclature (used in the second version) in parentheses after the current nomenclature (used in the third version).

- MODEL ORGANIZATION:
 - Specific concepts were grouped into levels of relevance.

- STRUCTURES:
 - Added the specific concept “Observatory” to the intermediate concept “Contents”.
 - Added the specific concept “Security” to the intermediate concept “Characteristics”.
 - Changed the description of the specific concept “Relationship” (contained in the intermediate concept “Components”) to include relationships with other systems.
 - Changed the description of the specific concept “Access” and “Partial Data” (both contained in the intermediate concept “Characteristics”) to make the difference between public and private data clearer.
 - Changed the description of the concept “Interactivity” (contained in the intermediate concept “Characteristics”) to include discussion forums.
 - Changed the nomenclature of the specific concept “Dissemination” (Output) contained in the intermediate concept “Components”.

- LAW SUIT:
 - Changed the nomenclature of the specific concepts “Transform” (Analyze) contained in the intermediate concept “Produce Knowledge and Intelligence”.
 - The specific concepts “Debate” and “Interact”, contained in the intermediate concept “Produce Knowledge and Intelligence”, were grouped into “Interact”

- AGENTS:
 - The specific concepts “Transparency”, “Visibility” and “Monitoring”, contained in the intermediate concept “Motivations” were grouped under “Transparency”.
 - The specific concepts “Control” and “Accountability”, contained in the intermediate concept “Motivations” were grouped under “Control”.